

Relative Acidity of 5-Hydroxyperinaphthindane-1,3-dione

A. K. BHATTAMISHRA*, B. C. MAHANTA†, K. K. MUKHERJEE‡ and M. K. ROUT**

Physical Metallurgy Division, National Metallurgical Laboratory, Jamshedpur-831 007

Manuscript received 19 August 1985, accepted 24 December 1985

Synthesis of *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene dyes derived from 5-hydroxyperinaphthindane-1,3-dione and various acidic nuclei have been described. Utilising their absorption maxima data and that of dimethinmerocyanines and by applying Brooker's deviation theory relative acidity of 5-hydroxyperinaphthindane-1,3-dione and other acidic nuclei have been established.

SIMILAR to merocyanines, benzylidene dyes are of great importance in dye chemistry. Just as the merocyanines are regarded as the structural hybrid of symmetrical cyanine and oxonol, the benzylidene derivatives of the cyclic keto methylene compound (perinaphthindane-1,3-dione, **1** in this case) **2** may be regarded as the structural hybrid of Micher's hydroly blue (**3**) and the corresponding oxonol (**4**).

(1)

(2)

(3)

(4)

Experimental

5-Hydroxyperinaphthindane-1,3-dione (**1**) selected for this investigation was prepared according to the method of Black *et al.*¹. Preparation of 2-(acetanilidomethylene) and 2-(3'-acetanilidoallylidene) intermediate of 5-hydroxyperinaphthindane-1,3-dione, merocyanines and oxonols have been described in our previous paper².

2-(*p*-Dimethylaminobenzylidene)-5-hydroxyperinaphthindane-1,3-dione: 5-Hydroxyperinaphthindane-1,3-dione (0.4 g) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.30 g) were refluxed in acetic anhydride for 30 min. On cooling, the product separated out and it was crystallised from ethanol, yield (70%), m.p. 220°; $\lambda_{\max}$ 485 nm.

Utilising the $\lambda_{\max}$ data of the above dyes the deviations were calculated according to Brooker and Keyes³.

Results and Discussion

Relative acidity from the deviation of dimethin merocyanines: In order to find out the relative acidity of perinaphthindane-1,3-dione, the $\lambda_{\max}$ values of the dimethin merocyanines and deviations derived from a fixed basic nucleus, *i.e.* benzothiazole and variable acidic nuclei are compared. From Table 1, it is evident that the acidity of different nuclei decreases in the order: chroman-2,4-dione > thia-chroman-2,4-dione > 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone > indan-1,3-dione > perinaphthindane-1,3-dione > 3-phenylrhodanine.

Relative acidity from the deviation of benzylidene dyes: The previous conclusion can also be attained by comparing the $\lambda_{\max}$ values of *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene dyes derived from perinaphthindane-1,3-dione and other acidic nuclei with fixed amino-benzaldehydic nucleus (Table 2). From Table 2 it is evident that acidity decreases in the order: chroman-2,4-dione > thiachroman-2,4-dione > 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone > indan-1,3-dione > perinaphthindane-1,3-dione > 3-phenylrhodanine.

† Khalikot College, Berahampur.

‡ F. M. College, Balasore.

** Ex-Vice-Chancellor, Utkal University.

TABLE 1

Nature of nucleus 'A'	λ_{max} (nm)				
	Symmetrical trimethin cyanine of benzothiazole	Symmetrical monomethin oxonol ion of 'A'	Calculated	Observed	Deviation
Perinaphthindane-1,3-dione	565	480	522.5	500	22.5
3-Phenylrhodanine	565	520	542.5	510	32.5
Indan-1,3-dione	565	455	510	494	16.0
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone	565	448	504	490	14.0
Thiachroman-2,4-dione	565	480	497.5	485	12.5
Chroman-2,4-dione	565	480	497.5	490	7.5

TABLE 2

Nature of nucleus 'A'	λ_{max} (nm)				
	Micher's hydrol blue	Symmetrical methin oxonol ion of 'A'	Calculated	Observed	Deviation
Perinaphthindane-1,3-dione	606	480	543	485	58
3-Phenylrhodanine	606	520	563	480	83
Indan-1,3-dione	606	455	530.5	475	55.5
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone	606	448	524.5	470	54.5
Thiachromandione	606	480	518	490	28.0
Chroman-2,4-dione	606	480	518	505	13.0

Thus, from the above studies it is also confirmed that either in a series of merocyanines or benzylidene dyes, deviation is maximum for the least acidic nucleus which agrees well with the Brooker's theory of deviation.

References

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